

SOLAR CONCENTRATORS' DEVELOPMENTS IN NIGERIA: A REVIEW.

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ABSTRACT

The use of concentrators in the forms of solar energy collectors in order to concentrate sunrays for better usage is on the increase world wide. To this effect, different types of solar concentrators have been developed over the years for various applications. The present study reviewed the various solar concentrators developed in Nigeria such as the parabolic fresnel concentrator, paraboloid solar cooker, parabolic trough collector, conical concentrator, compound parabolic solar concentrator and solar tracking bi-focal collectors. It identified their level of performance and limitations, and proposed suggestions for further improvement. The needs for support by adequate funding through research grants and patronage by governments, corporate bodies and individuals was emphasized.

KEYWORDS: Solar, Energy, Collector, Concentrator, Development, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The environmental consequences of utilizing fossil and nuclear fuels, and the advantages of solar and other renewable energy resources have been highlighted in such world fora as the United Nations Conference on New and Renewable Sources of Energy held in Nairobi in 1981, the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 and World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD) in Johannesburg (Iloje, 1997).

Solar radiation has been identified as the largest renewable resource on earth. This energy source is more evenly distributed in the Sunbelt of the world than wind or biomass, allowing for more site locations (Muller-Steinhagen, 2003). The maximum intensity of solar radiation at the earth's surface is about 1.2 kW/m² but it is encountered only near the equator on clear days at noon. Under these ideal conditions, the total energy received is from 6 - 8 kW h/m² per day (Halacy, 1980; Androsky, 1973; Spillman et al., 1979). Solar energy is not available continuously because of the day/night cycle and cloud cover. Its intensity varies according to season, geographical location, and position of the collector.

Solar energy can be applied in different ways and also many different methods for collecting the solar energy from incident radiation are available. The use of sunlight directly as an energy source has proved in the past to be less economical than the use of these other sources of concentrated sunshine in the forms of solar energy collectors. Solar collectors developed over the year can be categorized as concentrating or focusing collectors, flat plate collectors, solar ponds and photovoltaic panels. Literatures have shown that concentrating or focusing collectors are much older than flat plate collectors (David, 1979; Garg, 1982).

This study examines various developments in solar concentrators in Nigeria. It identifies, describes and reports on various categories of solar concentrators developed and their present limitation.

SOLAR RADIATION AVAILABILITY IN NIGERIA

It is normally estimated that areas of the world lying between latitudes 35°N and 35°S of the equator and which have at least 200 hours of bright Sunshine per year are ideal for the utilization of the sun's energy. Nigeria, located between latitudes 4°N and 14°N of the equator is very much within this area. The abundance of solar energy is best quantified in terms of the available average irradiation, and hours of sunshine and frequency of overcast. A reasonable amount of work has been done to quantify and predict the status of solar radiation availability in Nigeria by research centers, institutions and various individuals. Sambo and Doyle (1980) carried out extrapolation of the monthly radiation data of a number of Nigeria cities from measured data of some other locations. And an empirical model for the correlation of global solar radiation with meteorological data for Northern Nigeria has been carried out by Sambo (1986).

Layi Fagbenle (1990) carried out estimation of monthly mean daily total solar radiation of 16 selected cities within Nigeria. Estimates of the total solar radiation was obtained from meteorological data such as hours of insolation, percentage of possible insolation or cloudiness, relative humidity, number of rainy days in a given period etc. The paper compared various forms of two major relationships in an attempt to find those best suited to estimate total solar radiation of these cities. Ojosu (1989) has presented the Iso-radiation map of Nigeria, while Onyegegbu (1993) reported the global radiation measurement, direct radiation measurement and diffuse radiation measurement of various locations in Nigeria. Layi Fagbenle and Karayiannis (1994) have carried out the harmonic analysis of monthly solar radiation in Nigeria. Also, fourier analysis of climatological data series in a Nigeria Tropical environment has been done by Layi Fagbenle (1995).

Results of these various studies show that the country is endowed with reasonable amount of solar energy. Summary given by Aliyu (1998) shows that the Total annual solar energy received is 5×10^{12} kWh, Range of mean daily radiation is 15.4 – 22.6 MJ/m² – day, Range of mean daily sunshine is 3.5-7.0 hrs, and Range of Mean daily overcast is 1.5 – 5.5 hrs. These values are high on the average for the whole country but relatively higher in the Northern part of the country. These have made solar energy to generate and attract attention in Nigeria, hence, the on going local research efforts to utilize the solar energy resource.

DEVELOPMENTS IN SOLAR ENERGY CONCENTRATORS IN NIGERIA

Based on the available literature and materials, a number of researchers have carried out various works on concentrating solar collectors in Nigeria some are reported below.

1. Parabolic fresnel concentrator: Musa et al. (1992) carried out the design, construction and performance test of a parabolic fresnel concentrator cooker using locally available materials. The design of the concentrator cooker was based on the fresnel principle which consists of concentric parabolic rings – frustums of cones. These components were arranged on a flat structure having the same focus and properties for light perpendicular to their axis or revolution. Glass mirrors were used as the reflective material. The pot was placed on a grill fixed at the focal point of the concentration which is suspended such that it rotates freely about the focal axis. In this way, the pot remains stationary irrespective of tracking angle setting. The concentrator presents a smaller amount of area to the wind compared to a parabolic dish concentrator, thereby promising greater stability and pot accessibility.

Tracking the sun with the concentrator is by manual adjustment at 20 minutes time interval for altitudinal change in the sun's position. Series of water boiling and controlled cooking tests carried out with the concentrator under various levels of atmospheric turbidity yielded very encouraging and satisfactory results. Though the fresnel concentrator performed satisfactorily despite a 34.3% reduction in reflective area compared to a paraboloid of the same diameter, the 20 minutes ritual needed for manual adjustment in order to track the sun proved to be a major disadvantage with this device.

2. Paraboloid solar cooker: Ajiya (1995) designed and constructed a paraboloid solar cooker at University of Maiduguri, Nigeria. The design was based on point focus using small square glass mirrors fixed on fabricated parabolic dish as the reflecting surface. The paraboloid is then placed on a mounting with some kind of steering arrangement that can be used to track the sun manually as it transverses its path from east to west. Blackened flat plate placed at the focal point serves as the absorber on which cooking pot is placed. Locally sourced materials were used for fabrication of the various parts. Testing revealed that the parabolic solar cooker performed at about 30% efficiency in Maiduguri environment.

A year latter, Mshelbwala (1996) carried out modification on Ajayi work in order to improve its efficiency. He introduced "L" shaped flat bars to replaced the blackened flat plate for the support of the cooking pot, and painted the bottom of cooking pot black. This modification made the bottom of the cooking pot to be the receiver thereby causing direct heating of the pot without any intermediary as was in the original design. Heat loss due to conduction between the flat-plate and cooking pot was eliminated by the new modification. Analysis of the data collected from the experimental tests carried out on the modified cooker revealed an efficiency of 46.6% which is an improvement on the earlier design. Pelemo et al. (2002a) have also carried out the design, construction and performance test of focusing type solar cooker at the Centre for Energy Research and Development, Obafemi Awolowo University (O.A.U.), Ile-Ife. Basic paraboloid equation were used in the design after due consideration of all necessary

environmental factors. The performance of the concentrator cooker constructed was found satisfactory in Ile-Ife environment. The layout is shown in figure 1.

Pelemo *et al.* (2002b) have noted the importance of materials used as shells for solar cooker. For their concentrators, the shell of the cooker were developed using various combinations of paper pulp with starch, sawdust and resins, and concrete cement. They considered cement mixed with sawdust and reinforced with palm fibers as a better alternative and more suitable for their environment. In their work, two types of materials were considered for use as the reflective material. These are aluminum sheet and glass mirrors. They concluded that both materials are suitable as reflective materials in Ile-Ife environment even though they have different years of effective service durations.

Pelemo *et al.* (2003) also demonstrated the application of solar concentration for water boiling and distillation in a Nigeria environment (Ile-Ife). Concentrator with rotatory paraboloid reflector was used in their work because of its capacity of delivering high focal temperature, large power and short cooking time couple with the simplicity of determining the focal spot. The concentrator was made to follow the guiding equation of the rotatory paraboloid, and was constructed based on the parabola whose focal point was 70cm. The concave part forming the reflector was obtained by sticking small pieces of glass mirrors onto the surface using coal tar. Tracking of the sun by the concentrator was done manually. Water boiling and distillation was achieved with the solar concentrator at Ile-Ife. In Bauchi, Nigeria, Dahiru *et al.* (2007) have carried out the development of a paraboloidal concentrating solar cooker with manually tracking device and tested under hazy weather condition. Maximum temperature of 91°C was attained during water boiling test. The layout of the solar cooker is shown in figure 2.

3. Parabolic Trough: Sulaiman *et al.* (1989) have designed and tested a low-cost cylindrical collector for steam generation which still requires further improvement. Also Ahmed (2001) carried out the design, fabrication and performance evaluation of an improved parabolic trough solar concentrating collector using slat-mirrors in Ahmadu Bello University (A.B.U.) Zaria, Nigeria. The design was based on parabolic trough concept and a prototype collector of aperture area of 1.2m² was constructed. The collector aperture area was made up of slat-mirrors or long piece of plane-reflecting surfaces as the focusing surface instead of continuous parabolic curve surface. While a parabolic curve metal sheet serves as the bed-material where the slat-mirrors were laid, uncovered circular pipe serves as the receiver. Bolted to the receiver pipe and the metal sheet are the rectangular frame structure and supporting bars that hold the metal sheet in a fixed geometry with the receiver located at the focal line. The sun tracking mechanism consisted of two angle-iron bar structures freely connected to convert linear displacement of a satellite dish jack arm bolted in between them into an angular motion of the collector as to align the sun rays. Performance evaluation based on water heating shows that the collector using slat-mirrors is over 75% efficient against its evaluation when collector with continuous curved surface is considered. The maximum flow temperature attained by the collector was 58°C, while the maximum hourly and daily efficiencies were evaluated to be close to 50% using data collected during tests in Zaria environment. The layout of the solar collector is shown in figure 3.

4. Conical Concentrator: Design, construction and estimation of performance of solar conical concentrator, composite conical concentrator and parabolic reflector have been carried out in some part of the country (Oyetunji and Sawhney, 1989; Oyetunji *et al.*, 1989; Gholap and Idikio, 1989). In order to improve on existing work on conical concentrator, another design and development of a solar conical concentrator was carried out by Daudu (2002) at Bayero University (B.U.K.) Kano, Nigeria. He designed and constructed an axicon concentrator of 100cm aperture, cone height of 46cm and vertex angle of 90°. The cone was developed from steel sheet of 0.6mm thickness and the inner surface aligned with 63 designed triangular plane mirror strips. Each strip is 5cm wide on the upper side and 1cm wide on the vertex side of the cone. Two absorbers of diameters 8cm and 6cm, and heights of 46cm and 47cm respectively were also designed and fabricated. The absorbers were painted black, filled with water and placed at the centre of the axicon mounted on an improvised mounting of modified common satellite stand. The sun tracking could only be achieved by adjusting an adjustable leg of the mounting stand manually at interval, which in turn tilts the axicon collector to the desired direction i.e. direction facing the sun. Rollers wheels were provided for the legs for easy movement of the unit as well as for azimuthally changes. When located in the sun, the temperature as high as 106°C were recorded. Though the solar collector is an energy saving device, it cannot be used as stand alone

5. equipment because of some inherent limitations which leave room for further improvement. The layout of the conical concentrator is shown in figure 4.

5. Compound parabolic solar concentrator: Asere et al. (2003) have carried out the design, construction and testing of a compound parabolic solar cooker (CPC) at A.T.B.U. Bauchi. The temperature of up to 90°C was obtained while highest instantaneous efficiency of the cooker for the clear day was 44%. The layout of the compound parabolic cooker is shown in figure 5. The effect of spherical scatters on the thermal performance of the CPC was found to be quite high even when the particles are assumed to be non-absorbing. And in order to boost the energy available for cooking, the need of energy storage in the CPC system has been suggested (Habou et al. 2003).

6. Solar Tracking Bi-Focal Collectors. A solar tracking bi-focal collector system shown in figure 6 has been designed, constructed and tested for the purpose of heating water by Abdulrahim (2008). The collectors were made of two paraboloid concentrators, each having an aperture area of 1.53m², aperture diameter of 1.4m, depth of 0.145m, focal length of 0.84m, receiver diameter of 0.3m and a concentration ratio of 22. For the construction of the solar collectors, mild steel- sheet and square pipe were used as the shell support for the reflecting surfaces, while the concave parts forming the reflectors were obtained by sticking small pieces of glass mirrors on to the surface of the shell using glue.

The tracking mode adopted is the mechanical clockwork system using chains and sprockets. Framework support structure was provided for the solar collector system using equal angle mild steel and pipe and the water supply system comprises of an elevated tank, structural support, pipe networks, fittings and hoses. Performance evaluation of the solar collectors carried out in Maiduguri revealed that minimum outlet water temperature of 42°C was recorded during the month of December, while the temperature rose to 78°C in March and September. The highest temperature attained during the test period was 83°C when using a modified receiver to heat 8 liters of water at the focal zone of the collectors in March. Review of the design considerations and material selection, and modification of the receiver geometry are highly recommended. Effects of collectors' position and load types on the performance of the solar tracker should be further investigated.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Past work on solar focusing collectors in Nigeria employed the use of polish parabolic curved surface to form the focusing surface of the collectors while in some cases small pieces of mirror plates were placed on the parabolic curved surface. The tracking modes range from manually tracking to automated mode of tracking. Attention has also been given to support system for the collectors when necessary. The solar concentrators developed have a wide range of applications such as water heating, steam generation, water distillation, solar refrigeration, and cooking of food items. A common theme arising from the available literature is the need for further improvement of these developed solar concentrators through modification of component parts and detailed study of their performance under varying operational conditions. Supports in form of research grants, and patronage of these developed solar concentrators is highly recommended.

Figure 1: Focusing-type Solar cooking device (Pelemo et al., 2002a)

Figure 2: Concentrating Solar Energy Cooker (Dahiru et al., 2007)

Figure 3: Solar trough collector (Ahmed, 2001)

Figure 4: Solar Conical Concentrator (Dauda, 2002)

- 1 Reflecting Surfaces 3 Wooden box 5 Absorber 7 Booster mirror
- 2 Glass Cover 4 Insulation 6 Air-gap

Figure 5: Cross-section of Concentrating compound parabolic cooker (Asere et al., 2003)

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